

AN INVESTIGATION ON MULTIFUNCTIONAL PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE SPARS FOR ENERGY HARVESTING IN UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES

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SUMMARY

This paper investigates the combination of structural functionality with power generation and storage capability to form self-charging piezoelectric composite energy harvesters for use in UAVs. Multifunctional energy harvesting spars offer a reduction in the added mass and volume of conventional harvesters which is critical for UAV applications.

Keywords: Multifunctional materials, self-charging, energy harvesting, piezoelectric, unmanned aerial vehicle, thin-film batteries

INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in low power electronics have encouraged the development of energy harvesting systems capable of scavenging ambient energy surrounding a system. A focus has been placed on piezoelectric harvesting of vibration energy and this topic has received much attention in the research community [1]. An interesting application of energy harvesting technology is the powering of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) and micro air vehicles (MAVs) utilizing solar and vibration energy sources [2, 3]. Solar transduction using photovoltaic materials offers generous power output, however, solar harvesting is capable of generating energy only during daytime flight. Piezoelectric energy harvesting can generate usable electrical energy anytime ambient vibration energy is available either during flight or while perched on a vibrating surface. In either case, energy harvesting can be used to supplement the fuel supply or power an electronic component of UAVs with the goal of extending the endurance of the aircraft. Research has also been conducted on the use of solar, wind, electromagnetic, and thermal energy harvesting for UAVs as well as selfconsuming battery implementations by Thomas et al [4].

Previously, the authors have investigated the use of photovoltaic and piezoelectric harvesting in a small RC glider aircraft similar in size to currently available UAVs [2]. As is common with typical energy harvesting applications, the piezoelectric devices and solar panels were designed as add-on components to the host system. It is the goal of

this research to investigate a multifunctional approach to energy harvesting in which the harvesting system is integrated into the design of the aircraft and is capable of scavenging and storing electrical energy, and supporting structural loads. By designing the harvester into the aircraft, it can be used to replace a structural member (or portion thereof) of the host system, thus reducing the total mass addition of the harvester.

Recently, the authors have introduced the concept of multifunctional *self-charging structures* containing piezoelectric devices for energy harvesting and thin-film lithium-based batteries for energy storage as well as basic design factors for modifying a UAV wing spar with restrictions on the allowable change in mass and strength of the spar [5, 6]. This paper focuses on the integration of self-charging structures into a representative UAV wing spar. A Rayleigh-Ritz electromechanical formulation is first developed to model multilayer, segmented piezoelectric energy generator beams. The model is used to predict the coupled vibration and voltage response of the harvesters. Two case studies are presented in this work. First, a simple multilayer composite self-charging structure is investigated to introduce the concept. Next, a representative carbon fiber wing spar is modified to include piezoelectric elements for energy generation and thin-film batteries for energy storage. In both case studies, the self-charging composite structures are fabricated and experimentally tested. Results from experimentation are compared to the predictions from the Rayleigh-Ritz model.

MULTIFUNCTIONAL SPAR CONCEPT

Conventional energy harvesting systems are applied as add-on components, often adding a significant amount of mass and volume to the host structure. The performance and efficiency of UAV and MAV systems are highly dependent on the mass and aerodynamics of the aircraft, thus a multifunctional approach in which an energy harvesting system is designed as an integral component of the aircraft is adopted to reduce any adverse effects of incorporating the harvester into the host structure. The proposed self-charging composite harvester, shown in Figure 1(a), contains both energy generation and energy storage capability in a multi-layered platform. The device contains two piezoelectric layers for energy generation, two thin-film battery layers for energy storage, and a central structural layer. The operational principle behind the composite involves simultaneous harvesting of electrical energy in the piezoelectric layer when subjected to loadings that cause deformations in the structure as well as energy storage in the thin film battery layers embedded in the device. Energy is transferred directly between the piezoelectric layers and thin film battery layers through conditioning circuitry, thus a single device is capable of both generating and storing electrical energy all while carrying load as a structural member. This compact composite structure can be considered as the wing or wing spar in UAV and micro air vehicle (MAV) applications, as shown in Figure 1(b).

In order for the proposed self-charging structures to be embedded into a host structure and carry load, both the active harvesting material and the storage device must be capable of supporting load without failure. Conventional storage devices such as capacitors, supercapacitors, and batteries are not suitable for direct integration into the

Figure 1: (a) Schematic of composite self-charging structure; (b) self-charging wing spar.

self-charging structure as the mechanical loading experienced by the structure would likely damage the storage element. Recent developments in the area of lithium-based batteries yield the discovery of flexible thin-film lithium batteries with thicknesses on the order of fractions of millimeters and capacities in the milliamp-hour range for a 25 mm x 25 mm device. These thin-film batteries present a breakthrough in storage element technology as they are much smaller and lighter than conventional storage devices, and they are flexible. In order to best utilize these thin-film lithium batteries, it is proposed to embed them directly into the harvester, shown previously in Figure 1(a), to create a compact, multifunctional device capable of generating and storing electrical energy, and carrying structural loads.

ELECTROMECHANICAL MODELING

Distributed-parameter analytical solutions for cantilevered unimorph [7], bimorph [8] and multi-morph [6] power generator structures under base excitation have been presented in the recent literature. Convergence of the electromechanical Rayleigh-Ritz formulation [9] to the analytical solution given by Erturk and Inman [7] for sufficient number of kinematically admissible functions has been reported in a recent paper by Elvin and Elvin [10]. Rayleigh-Ritz formulation is a powerful technique for handling structures with variable geometry for which the exact (analytical) eigenfunctions are either difficult or impossible to obtain. The two-segment and five-segment multi-layer devices investigated in this work are modeled using the Rayleigh-Ritz technique. The following is a summary of the Rayleigh-Ritz type piezoelectric generator formulation (based on the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory) and detailed derivations can be found in Hagood et al [9], Elvin and Elvin [10] or duToit et al [11] among others. In this derivation, the cantilevered beam structure is assumed to be sufficiently thin so that the shear strain and rotary inertia effects are negligible for the practical vibration modes of interest (the fundamental mode is of particular interest in energy harvesting). The negligibly thin electrode pairs covering the opposite faces of piezoceramic layer(s) are assumed to be perfectly conductive so that a single potential difference (voltage) can be defined across them.

The governing equations of a piezoelectric generator can be obtained from Hamilton's principle for electromechanical media as

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{r}}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{r}}(t) + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{r}(t) - \mathbf{\Theta}v(t) = -\mathbf{M}^* a_B(t), \quad (1)$$

$$C_p \dot{v}(t) + \frac{v(t)}{R_l} + \Theta^T \dot{\mathbf{r}}(t) = 0, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{K} are the mass, damping and stiffness matrices, Θ is the electromechanical coupling vector, \mathbf{M}^* is the effective forcing vector, C_p is the equivalent capacitance, R_l is the external load resistance, $\mathbf{r}(t)$ is the modal mechanical response, $v(t)$ is the voltage response across the load resistance, a_B is the base acceleration of the harvester, and an over-dot represents differentiation with respect to time. Here, proportional damping is assumed so that standard modal analysis can be used with mathematical convenience (i.e., the damping matrix has the form $\mathbf{C} = \alpha\mathbf{M} + \beta\mathbf{K}$ where α and β are constants of proportionality). Elements of the mass, stiffness, damping, effective forcing, and electromechanical coupling matrices and vectors in the absence of lumped mass and spring attachments are

$$M_{ij} = \int_V \rho \phi_i(x) \phi_j(x) dV, \quad K_{ij} = \int_V Y z^2 \phi_i''(x) \phi_j''(x) dV, \quad C_{ij} = \alpha M_{ij} + \beta K_{ij},$$

$$M_i^* = \int_V \rho \phi_i(x) dV, \quad \theta_i = \int_V \frac{Y^E d_{31}}{h_p} z \phi_i''(x) dV. \quad (3)$$

Here, V is the volume, ρ is the mass density, and Y is the elastic modulus (at constant electric field for piezoceramic) of a point in the structure, z is the distance of the point from the neutral axis, d_{31} is the piezoelectric constant, h_p is the thickness of the piezoceramic, and a prime represents differentiation with respect to x (which is the axial position on the beam). A simple admissible function that satisfies the essential boundary conditions of a clamped-free beam is [10]

$$\phi_i(x) = 1 - \cos\left(\frac{(2i-1)\pi x}{2L}\right), \quad (4)$$

where i is the modal index. Note that one should use sufficient number of admissible functions for convergence of the natural frequencies of interest to the exact values.

Physical vibration response of the beam relative to its vibrating base is then

$$w(x,t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i(x) r_i(t) = \Phi^T(x) \mathbf{r}(t), \quad (5)$$

where $\Phi(x)$ is the vector of admissible functions and N is the total number of mechanical modes used in the expansion.

If the base acceleration is assumed to be harmonic of the form $a_B(t) = \bar{a}_B e^{j\omega t}$ (where ω is the excitation frequency and j is the unit imaginary number), the steady-state voltage response and the vibration response can be obtained from Eqs. (1) and (2) as

$$v(t) = j\omega \left(\frac{1}{R_l} + j\omega C_p \right)^{-1} \Theta^T \left(\mathbf{K} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M} - j\omega \mathbf{C} + j\omega \left(\frac{1}{R_l} + j\omega C_p \right)^{-1} \Theta \Theta^T \right)^{-1} \mathbf{M}^* \bar{a}_B e^{j\omega t}, \quad (6)$$

$$w(x,t) = -\Phi^T(x) \left(\mathbf{K} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M} - j\omega \mathbf{C} + j\omega \left(\frac{1}{R_l} + j\omega C_p \right)^{-1} \Theta \Theta^T \right)^{-1} \mathbf{M}^* \bar{a}_B e^{j\omega t}. \quad (7)$$

Here, the voltage output – to – base acceleration and the vibration response – to – base acceleration FRFs (frequency response functions) can be extracted as $v(t)/\bar{a}_B e^{j\omega t}$ and $w(x,t)/\bar{a}_B e^{j\omega t}$, respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL TESTING AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Two self-charging composite energy harvesting structures are fabricated, tested, and modeled in this study. A simple multilayer structure containing two piezoelectric layers, two thin-film battery layers, and a central metallic shim layer is first investigated (Figure 2(a)). This device serves as a test bed to evaluate the concept of self charging structures in its simplest form. Next, a carbon fiber beam representative of a typical lightweight, stiff aircraft spar is modified to include piezoelectric and battery layers to form a self-charging wing spar (Figure 2(b)). Each of the self-charging structures consists of two QuickPack QP10N piezoelectric devices (Midé Technology Corp., Medford, MA), and two Thinerger MEC101-7SES thin-film batteries (Infinite Power Solutions, Inc., Littleton, CO), shown in Figure 3(a), bonded to a substrate in a bimorph configuration. Each layer is bonded separately using 3M ScotchWeld™ DP460 2-part epoxy and cured using a vacuum bagging procedure to provide thin, uniform bonding layers. The QP16N devices have dimensions 50.8 mm x 25.4 mm x 0.343 mm and a mass of 1.35 g, and the Thinerger batteries have dimensions of 25.4 mm x 25.4 mm x 0.178 mm, a mass of 0.45 g, an operating voltage of 4.1 V, and a capacity of 0.7 mAh.

Prior to bonding of the Thinerger batteries, the performance of the batteries in both charging and discharging is evaluated. Charging is performed using a constant voltage charging method as recommended by the manufacturer by supplying 4.1 V to the battery using a power supply until only about 35 μ A of current is sourced by the battery. Discharge performance is obtained by applying a resistive load of 2749 Ω across the battery in order to draw roughly 2C of current (2 times the rated 0.7 mAh capacity, i.e. 1.4 mA) until a voltage of 3.0V is reached. Both the battery voltage and the current in/out of the battery are monitored during testing. By integrating the current over time during charging and discharging, the amount of energy flowing through the battery can

Figure 2: Photographs of (a) multilayer self-charging structure and (b) carbon fiber self-charging wing spar.

Figure 3: (a) Photograph of Thinerger thin-film battery; Characteristic performance curves of Thinerger batteries in (a) charging and (b) discharging.

be quantified in terms of a capacity in milliamp-hours (mAh). Similar calculations are presented by Pereira et al [12] when testing comparable thin-film batteries under static flexural deflections. The charge/discharge performance curves along with the calculated capacities are given in Figure 3(b) and Figure 3(c). It can be observed from the results that in both charging and discharging, the full 0.7 mAh capacity of the battery can be obtained.

Case 1 – Multilayer Self-Charging Device

The first device investigated is a simple multilayer composite self-charging structure, previously shown in Figure 2(a), containing a 0.076 mm thick brass substrate layer with QP16N piezoelectric devices bonded on both sides, and Thinerger MEC101-7SES batteries bonded to the outermost layers. This device is modeled as well as experimentally tested. The frequency response behavior of the device is first derived using the Rayleigh-Ritz model for various resistive electrical loads and then obtained experimentally by exciting the device harmonically using a small shaker (Figure 5(a)). For series connection of the piezoceramic layers, the model predicted and experimental voltage output – to – base acceleration FRFs of the generator are shown in Figure 4(a) for a set of resistive electrical loads (the base acceleration is given in terms of the gravitational acceleration, $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$). 30 modes are used in the Rayleigh-Ritz solution ($N = 30$) to ensure convergence of the natural frequencies (particularly the first one) using the admissible functions given by Eq. (4). With changing load resistance

Figure 4: (a) Voltage-to-base acceleration FRFs of the multilayer generator and (b) power vs. load resistance for excitation at the fundamental short circuit resonance frequency (147.5 Hz).

(from $100\ \Omega$ to $1\ \text{M}\Omega$), the experimental value of the fundamental resonance frequency moves from 144.5 Hz (close to short-circuit conditions) to 147.5 Hz (close to open-circuit conditions). These two frequencies are predicted by the model as 144.5 Hz and 148.5 Hz, respectively. The maximum voltage output is obtained for the largest load resistance at 147.5 Hz as 94.8 V/g in the experiments. Figure 4(b) displays the variation of the electrical power with load resistance for excitation at the short circuit resonance frequency (147.5 Hz) of the device. Among the set of resistors used in the experiments, a maximum power of $25.6\ \text{mW/g}^2$ is extracted from the generator for an electrical load of $6.7\ \text{k}\Omega$. The model predictions underestimate the power output at this fixed excitation frequency (145.7 Hz) since the resonance frequency shift from the short-circuit to the open-circuit conditions is lower than the theory in the experiment. Possibly due to imperfections in bonding (the theory assumes no shear between the layers), the theoretical resonance frequency shift (which is a measure of the overall piezoelectric coupling of the device) is larger than the experimental case.

With the frequency response behavior of the system obtained, the energy harvesting performance of the device is analyzed. The piezoelectric layers are connected in series and used to charge a single Thinerger battery through a simple energy harvesting circuit containing a bridge rectifier, voltage regulator (to limit the output voltage to 4.1 V), and smoothing capacitor. The self-charging structure is excited harmonically at the fundamental resonance frequency obtained with the device connected to the circuit (148 Hz) with an acceleration amplitude of $\pm 1.0\ g$ using the experimental setup shown in Figure 5(a). The charge/discharge performance curves as well as the calculated capacities are given in Figure 5(b) and Figure 5(c). From the results, it can be seen that an average of about $80\ \mu\text{A}$ of current and $0.29\ \text{mW}$ of power is delivered to the battery throughout the charge test. A total of $0.292\ \text{mAh}$ of capacity is delivered to the cell in a 4 hour time period. Upon discharging the battery at a rate of 1C ($0.7\ \text{mA}$) through a $5524\ \Omega$ resistor, the cell is able to provide the rated current output for about 1600 seconds before the voltage drops below 3.0 V. A total capacity of $0.246\ \text{mAh}$ is drawn from the battery, showing that almost all of the energy input to the battery from the piezoelectric devices in charging is available for use in discharging.

Case 2 – Self-Charging Carbon Fiber Wing Spar

The second device investigated is a modified self-charging carbon fiber wing spar, previously shown in Figure 2(b), which consists of a commercially available 3.13 mm thick carbon fiber composite substrate with QP16N piezoelectric devices and Thinerger MEC101-7SES batteries bonded to both sides of a machined section of the beam such that the device thickness remains fairly constant over the length. Again, the device is modeled and tested experimentally on a large shaker (Figure 7(a)). The symmetric multi-layer generator consists of 5 segments in the longitudinal direction. From the clamped end to the free end, the first segment is a 25.4 mm carbon fiber segment with the original thickness (3.13 mm) of the beam. The second segment is a 9.5 mm long carbon fiber transition segment with a reduced thickness of approximately 1.3 mm (effective value estimated on the machined surface). The third segment is a 25.4 mm segment with the 1.3 mm thick carbon fiber bracketed by the piezoceramic layers (along with Kapton and epoxy layers). The fourth segment is also a 25.4 mm segment and it

Figure 5: (a) Multilayered self-charging structure mounted on shaker; Experimental curves for self-charging structure in (b) charging and (c) discharging.

has the battery layers in addition to the piezoceramic layers. The fifth segment is a 168.0 mm long carbon fiber segment with the original beam thickness. For this 5-segment structure, 40 modes are used in the Rayleigh-Ritz solution procedure with a focus on the convergence of the first natural frequency. The simple admissible function given by Eq. (4) is used in the calculations as in the previous case study. The upper and the lower piezoceramic layers are connected in series for the frequency response measurements. Figure 6(a) displays the analytical and experimental voltage FRFs of the generator per base acceleration input for a range of resistors (from $100\ \Omega$ to $1\ \text{M}\Omega$). The experimental short-circuit and open-circuit resonance frequencies of the generator beam are obtained as 27.8 Hz and 28 Hz, respectively. These two frequencies are estimated using the model as 27.8 Hz and 28.2 Hz. The maximum voltage in Figure 6(a) is obtained at 28 Hz for the largest electrical load as 458.3 V/g. For excitation at the short circuit resonance frequency (27.8 Hz), the experimentally obtained and the theoretically predicted power versus load resistance diagrams are shown in Figure 6(b). The maximum power output of the device is obtained as 454.3 mW/g² for the best resistor (90 k Ω) among the ones used. The theory underestimates the power output for excitation at the short-circuit resonance frequency as in the previous case.

The charge/discharge performance of the self-charging carbon fiber wing spar is also tested experimentally. Similar to the previous case study, the piezoelectric layers are connected in series to charge a single thin-film battery through the same energy harvesting circuit used previously. The spar is excited harmonically at the fundamental

Figure 6: (a) Voltage-to-base acceleration FRFs of the carbon fiber spar and (b) power vs. load resistance for excitation at the fundamental short circuit resonance frequency (27.8 Hz).

Figure 7: (a) Self-charging carbon fiber wing spar mounted on shaker; Experimental curves for wing spar in (b) charging and (c) discharging.

resonance frequency obtained when connected to the circuit (28 Hz) with a base acceleration amplitude of $\pm 0.1 g$ using the experimental setup shown in Figure 7(a). The charge/discharge performance curves and calculated capacities are given in Figure 7(b) and Figure 7(c). The charge curve shows an average current of about 80 μA , average power of 0.27 mW, and a total capacity of 0.281 mAh delivered to the battery throughout the 4 hour test. Results of the discharge test (1C rate through a 5524 Ω resistor) show that the cell is able to provide the rated current output of 0.7 mA for about 1100 seconds before the voltage drops to 3.0 V. A total capacity of 0.210 mAh is drawn from the battery, again showing that most of the energy input to the battery from the piezoelectric devices can be used during discharging to power an electronic device.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The concept of multifunctional self-charging composite energy harvesting devices is applied to UAV and MAV wing spars in this research. A Rayleigh-Ritz formulation is developed to model the behaviour of both the simple multilayer harvester and the segmented carbon fiber wing spar harvester. Comparisons to experimental testing have been used to validate the accuracy of the model in predicting the vibration and voltage response of the devices under harmonic excitation. The energy harvesting performance of the self-charging structures is also obtained experimentally. It is found that in each case, the piezoelectric layers are able to charge the thin-film battery to about 40% capacity in 4 hours at reasonable excitation amplitudes. Overall, the results of this research have proven the ability to integrate self-charging piezoelectric structures into representative wing spars offering a multifunctional approach to energy harvesting in UAV and MAV applications. Future work is underway to characterize the mechanical strength and load bearing capability of the self charging structures. Static and dynamic strength testing of the harvester design will be performed to determine the robustness of the devices in typical aircraft applications.

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